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Firm Characteristics and Property, Plant and Equipment (PPE) of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This work empirically investigated the relationship between firm characteristics and PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study is vital as it portrays the extent to which firm characteristics influence the property, plant and equipment of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using panel regression model. The research design used is Ex Post Facto design and data for the study were obtained from the published annual financial reports of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria spanning from 2014-2023. The findings generally indicate that firm size and firm profitability have positive and significant effect on PPE of list non-financial firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. On the other hand, a positive and an insignificant relationship was found between firm age and PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. The study therefore concludes that firm characteristics determines PPE among the listed firms in Nigeria. In lieu of the findings of the study, it was recommended that firms should prioritize scaling their operations through strategic growth initiatives such as mergers, acquisitions, and market expansions to enhance their capacity for fixed asset acquisition. The significant role of profitability in driving PPE investments underscores the need for firms to focus on cost management, revenue optimization, and operational efficiency to enhance their profitability and reinvestment capacity. As firm age was not a significant factor, older firms should leverage their experience and industry knowledge to innovate and adapt, while younger firms should focus on agility and resource optimization to compete effectively.

Keywords: PPE; Firm Size; Firm Profitability; Firm Age

1. INTRODUCTION

Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) play a vital role in the operational and financial structure of non-financial firms worldwide (Dabic & Lamotte, 2017). These long-term tangible assets, which include land, buildings, machinery, and equipment, are integral to the production process and contribute significantly to firms' revenue generation and overall performance. The accurate accounting and disclosure of PPE are essential for reflecting the true financial position of firms. However, factors influencing the management, valuation, and disclosure of PPE are complex and multifaceted, often depending on both global and local dynamics (Gray & Dean, 2019).

Globally, the accounting standards governing PPE have undergone significant evolution, especially with the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). IFRS 16, which pertains to leases, and IAS 16, which relates to the measurement and depreciation of PPE, have introduced strict guidelines

on how firms should report and disclose their tangible assets (Alfredson, Leo, Picker, & Loftus, 2019). These standards have had profound implications, especially for non-financial firms that rely heavily on these assets for their day-to-day operations. The shift towards more transparent reporting aims to address issues of inconsistency and incomparability in financial statements across regions, enhancing investor confidence and financial market efficiency. According to Owolabi and Ilesanmi (2022), Nigerian firms, particularly in the non-financial sector, face unique challenges in managing their PPE. These challenges stem from unstable macroeconomic conditions, fluctuating exchange rates, inflationary pressures, and inconsistent power supply, all of which can affect the valuation and operational efficiency of tangible assets (Nwaobia & Alao, 2020). Furthermore, the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria has not been without challenges. Many firms struggle with compliance due to a lack of expertise, high costs of implementation, and inadequate regulatory oversight (Owolabi & Ilesanmi, 2022).

Regardless, technological advancements in asset management, particularly in manufacturing industries, require firms to continuously invest in upgrading their equipment to maintain competitiveness (Biddle, Hilary & Verdi, 2021). This is so because PPE represents a substantial portion of the total assets of Nigerian non-financial firms. Effective management and optimal use of these assets are therefore critical to ensuring sustained profitability and business longevity (Biddle, Hilary & Verdi, 2021). Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE), which includes machinery, buildings, and equipment, forms the core of a firm's production capacity. According to Chen, Lu, and Sougiannis (2012), "PPE is essential not only for establishing a firm's production capabilities but also for sustaining long-term growth and competitive advantage." This underscores the strategic importance of investing in and maintaining PPE.

In non-financial firms, PPE constitutes a substantial portion of the asset base, directly influencing their financial standing and creditworthiness. Firms with well-maintained PPE are often viewed more favorably by investors and lenders, as these assets can be leveraged on or liquidated when necessary. Conversely, poor conditions of PPE can lead to asset devaluation, which diminishes a firm's borrowing capacity and undermines investor confidence (Smith & Watts, 2014). Furthermore, inadequate PPE or insufficient investment in asset maintenance and replacement can trigger a cascade of operational challenges. This often results in increased operational costs, decreased productivity, and lower profitability. Wali (2015) highlights that "firms with outdated or inadequate equipment often experience higher downtime, inefficiency, and ultimately, a reduction in market competitiveness." This emphasizes the necessity for regular investments in PPE to ensure efficient and competitive operations.

Firm competitiveness is a vital element in assessing the overall performance and sustainability of non-financial firms, particularly in a dynamic economic environment. Competitive firms are those that can effectively manage their resources and optimize their operations to deliver products and services at a lower cost while maintaining quality. The Price-Cost Margin (PCM) is a widely used metric for evaluating firm competitiveness, as it reflects the difference between the price at which products are sold and the costs incurred in producing them. As noted by Simone (2022), "The Price-Cost Margin serves as an indicator of a firm's pricing power and operational efficiency, thereby providing insights into its competitive positioning in the market." Several studies explored have already established that a well-maintained asset base enhances operational efficiency, allowing firms to achieve higher PCM. For instance, Coad and Mazzucato (2013) found that firms that invest in modern and efficient PPE are better positioned to respond to market demands, leading to improved pricing strategies and profit margins. Additionally, firms with a robust PPE foundation often benefit from economies of scale, which can further enhance their competitive edge (Graham & Harvey, 2001).

The strategic management of PPE not only contributes to production efficiency but also plays a vital role in shaping a firm's competitive strategy. In highly competitive industries, firms must continuously assess their asset base and invest in upgrading equipment to maintain their market position. As suggested by Biddle et al. (2021), "Regular investment in PPE is essential for firms seeking to enhance their price-cost margins and sustain competitive advantages in an ever-evolving marketplace." Various factors influence the determination of PPE levels within firms, including firm size, capital structure, operational efficiency, managerial expertise, and firm competitiveness (Aguguom, Nwafor & Obi, 2022). Empirical evidence

from prior studies suggest that firms with larger asset bases are more likely to invest in PPE and disclose related information to attract investment, while smaller firms may be more conservative due to resource constraints (Afolabi & Olatunji, 2021).

Given the foregoing, this study seeks to explore the relationship between firm characteristics and PPE of quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria, with a focus on understanding the extent to which internal and external factors influence PPE investment and reporting, hence contributing to the existing literature by offering insights into the distinctive challenges faced by Nigerian firms in managing their tangible assets. To achieve this purpose, we formulated the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of firm size on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Firm age has no significant effect on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no statistically significant effect of firm profitability on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Property, Plants and Equipment (PPE)

Non-current asset investments are crucial for conducting operational activities and boost an organization's ability to deliver goods and services. These investment components comprise plant and machinery (office equipment, information and communication technology, buildings), motor vehicles, furniture, and fixtures (Omaliko et al., 2025; Akparhuere et al, 2019; Ullah & Ahmad, 2019; Jan Horas & Denny, 2019; Osirim & Moses, 2019; Thankgod, 2021; Anuar et al, 2021). Numerous factors justify why non-current assets are deemed crucial investment components within an organization. Okoro and Charles (2019) assert that strategic non-current asset investment is vital for firms to enhance shareholder value. A high non-current asset turnover ratio signifies effective non-current asset utilization in driving sales, whereas a low ratio suggests inefficient investment and asset use. Inadequate non-current asset investment can lead to subpar organizational performance (Anuar et al, 2021). Thriving organizations understand how to allocate resources to non-current assets for effective attainment of organizational objectives and respond to shifts in external environment and technological advancements (Mwaniki & Omagwa, 2017).

Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) are fundamentally long-term assets of a company, typically encompassing buildings and real estate, furniture, machinery, vehicles, and ICT infrastructure, including hardware and software (Investopedia, 2013). Non-current assets can be tangible or intangible. Olatunji and Adegbite (2014) found a direct correlation between non-current asset investment and performance, highlighting that such investment not only boosts profit generation but also plays a crucial role in daily firm operations. According to Magoulios (2006), the totality of the cost of economy involved in the purchase of new plants and machinery with the aim of increasing the stocks of raw materials and products for new homes is referred to as investment on a macroeconomic level. Philippa (2005) defines investment as a commitment of certain amount of money, in the present year, whose return is increased earnings in the future. Trujillo (2014) opines that investment in non-current assets like buildings, motor vehicles, and other equipment and so on determines the operational effectiveness of most industries. These non-current assets are normally shown on the statement of financial position and account for a large portion of a company's value.

There are varying perspectives on the significance of PPE within organizations. Some view PPE as critical assets that enable operational activities, enhance productivity, and contribute to long-term value creation. Others emphasize the financial implications of PPE, highlighting their role in financial reporting, asset valuation, and investment decision-making (Arya et al., 2017; Schipper, 2017). The current study adopted a multifaceted view of PPE, recognizing both their operational and financial significance. The study acknowledges PPE as essential assets that support organizational activities and contribute to value creation. Additionally, we emphasize the importance of PPE accounting methods in accurately reflecting the value of these assets in financial statements (Barth, 2018).

2.1.2 Firm Characteristics

Firm characteristics are factors that are largely under the control of management. It includes company size, liquidity, firm age, leverage and revenue growth. On the other hand, the macroeconomic indicators are such factors that are beyond management's control. These include interest rate, GDP and industry size (Omaliko & Okpala, 2023). Ali and Isa (2018) defined firm attributes as the distinctive features that distinguish one firm from another. It is possible to identify the characteristics of the company from the relevant information in the financial statements for a given accounting period (Stainer, 2006). According to Shehu and Bello (2013), firm attributes refer to the characteristics possessed by a particular company that defines its activities. It is composed of those variables that relatively influence company decisions extensively.

2.1.2.1 Firm Size

Firm size is measured by the total market share of any specific firm. Firm size is measured by taking the natural logarithm of total assets. The Size of the firm is basically considered in the analysis for the fact of diversification. The firm size measurement can be carried out in several methods namely through sales, employees, assets or value add features. Normally, those using the technological theory based on economy of scale derived from capital inputs would use only sales figures or assets for the measurement purpose. It has been found that sales and assets are not particularly apt methods of measurement for size; the main issue would be how agency, transactions and the range of costs impact the profits. Costs are normally related to the fundamental way the organization is controlled by a hierarchy more than just the value of physical assets. According to (Kaen& Baumann, 2003) in fact measuring the employee's enrolment and value-added measurement is a better choice in measuring the size of the firm in organizational theories rather than sales or assets. The value-added measurement is beneficial as it encompasses the complicated framework of a firm.

Niresh & Velnampy (2014) stated that a firm is represented by the amount and variety of its production capacity and the number of services it can currently offer to its customers. The size of a firm is a primary factor used in determining the performance of a company's activities because of the concept of economies of scale, which can be found in the traditional neoclassical view of the firm. Mesut (2013) says that a big firm has more competitive power when compared with small firms during the competition period. Furthermore, big firms are able to seize all the work opportunities during the time of competition, which require high capital rates since they have larger resources, and this situation provides them with better work opportunities to maximize their profit during the competition.

2.1.2.2 Profitability

The performance of a business can be evaluated based on its level of profitability (Pandey, 2004).The amount of debt indicates the growing requirement for exterior resources by the company and, consequently, the amount of profit that the company will use to settle the principal debt and the accumulated interest on them (Myers, 2001). Hence, the importance of profitability and the use of shareholders fund or equity fund cannot be overemphasized. This is because the company will not have to pay interest to any exterior resources provider for using the company funds (i.e., shareholders fund or equity fund) to finance its operating activities. A company or organization's fundamental Capital Structure will affect its profit-earning capacity (Reddy, 2012) and profit maximization is a required prerequisite for any firm that wants to sustain its going concern status, to the delight of its investors, administrators, and promoters. Many measures are used to evaluate a business: profitability, liquidity, turnover ratio, and other essential measurements. Profitability also can be measured using different financial ratios such as return on investment (ROI), cash ratio, return on assets (ROA) and other ratios. This study used ROA as a proxy and performance indicator for the profitability variable. This is because ROA is the portion of the profit for the accounting period that belongs to the owner of the company (Uzodimma et al., 2024).

Profit is the primary objective of a business (Nimalathan, 2009). Profit in the accounting sense tends to become a long-term objective which measures not only the success of the product, but also of the development of the market for it. It is determined by matching revenue against cost associated with it.

Only those costs are placed against revenue, which have a contribution in the generation of such revenue. An enterprise should earn profits to survive and grow over a long period of time. It provides evidence concerning the earnings potential of a company and how effectively a firm is being managed. If the enterprise fails to make profit, capital invested is eroded and if this situation prolongs the enterprise ultimately ceases to exist. Profit and profitability are two different terms. Profit is an absolute measure of earning capacity, while profitability is a relative measure of earning capacity (.

Profit is defined by Iyer (1995) as “excess of return over outlay” (Nimalathan, 2009) while profitability is defined as “the ability of a given investment to earn a return from its use”. The word profitability is composed of two words: profit and ability. The word profit has already been defined but the meaning of profit differs according to the use and purpose of the enterprise to earn the profits. Thus, the word profitability may be defined as the ability of a given investment to earn a return from its use. Profitability ratios assess a company's capacity to generate profits, serving as a key indicator for security analysis to shareholders and investors. Thus, profitability is the primary measure of the overall success of an enterprise. The analysis of profitability ratios is therefore important for the Shareholders, creditors, prospective investors, bankers, and government.

2.1.2.3 Firm Age

Firm age is a critical factor that influences various aspects of a company's operations and financial reporting. The age of a firm can significantly affect how it manages, reports, and discloses its Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE). Understanding the relationship between firm age and PPE determination is crucial for stakeholders, including investors, analysts, and regulators, as it provides insights into the asset management practices and financial health of the firm.

According to Ball (2006), the adoption and implementation of international accounting standards, such as IFRS, can be influenced by the age of the firm as older firms, with their established accounting systems and practices tends to face challenges in transitioning to new standards. However, these firms are also more likely to have the resources and experience necessary to comply with complex regulatory requirements. Compliance with IFRS, particularly IAS 16 for PPE, requires firms to adopt consistent and transparent accounting practices, which can improve the quality of financial reporting and enhance comparability across firms and industries (Ball, 2006).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Agency Theory

Agency theory, proposed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), explores the conflict of interest between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers). This theory is highly relevant to the management of Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) investments, which often involve significant capital expenditures with long-term implications for firms. Managers, acting as agents, might prioritize short-term gains or personal benefits over the long-term interests of shareholders, resulting in suboptimal allocation of resources to PPE.

For instance, a firm with weak governance structures may experience over- or under-investment in PPE due to managerial opportunism. Over-investment might occur when managers seek to grow the firm excessively for personal prestige, while under-investment could result from risk aversion or a focus on short-term performance metrics. Strong governance mechanisms, such as effective board oversight and appropriate executive compensation, can align managerial decisions with shareholder interests, ensuring that PPE investments are optimized to enhance firm value (DeFond & Zhang, 2022; Omaliko et al., 2023). Moreover, agency theory underscores the importance of transparency in reporting PPE-related transactions. Misalignment between managerial decisions and shareholders' expectations may lead to inaccurate depreciation estimates, impairments, or valuation issues, thereby affecting financial statements. The theory highlights the necessity for stringent internal controls and audit practices to ensure accountability in PPE management.

2.3 Empirical Review

Samson and Edidiong (2024) examined the relationship between property, plant and equipment measurement and financial reporting quality of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design with data collected through the administration of a five point Likert Scale questionnaire to a sample of 360 accounting staff across selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics tools and Pearson product moment correlation analysis via SPSS 25.0 statistical package. The study's findings revealed that PPE measurement using cost model has an insignificant positive relationship with faithful representation of financial information of manufacturing firms in Nigeria while PPE measurement using revaluation model has a significant positive relationship with faithful representation of financial information of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ogunbiyi and Adeyemo (2024) investigated the determining factors of sustainable property investment (SPI) in Lagos, Nigeria. Descriptive statistics was adopted for the study and the findings of the study suggested that the perceived benefits of SPI include: environmental satisfaction; freedom from noise disturbance; healthy indoor air quality; aesthetic appearance; increased property value; and reduced airborne particulates.

Osanyinbi, Siyannbola, Omoniyi and Iregha (2023) examined the concept of fair value measurement as well as determine its influence on the financial reporting quality of items in the financial statement of insurance companies. The study used survey method and questionnaire as research instrument to elicit data from professional accountants in selected listed insurance companies in Lagos state, using convenience sampling technique. The data collected were analyzed with the aid of SPSS. The study revealed that there is significant relationship between fair value measurement and the financial reporting quality and that the fair value measurement has significant influence on financial reporting quality at each level of the hierarchies.

Chen and Wang (2023) examined the role of firm profitability in driving PPE investments among Asian non-financial firms. Using a sample of 50 firms from 2015 to 2023, the study adopted a fixed-effects regression approach. Findings revealed that profitability significantly influenced fixed asset growth, with firms reinvesting profits into long-term projects to enhance operational efficiency and competitive advantage.

Ahmed and Bello (2023) examined how firm size influences fixed asset acquisition among listed industrial firms in Nigeria. Using data spanning 2012 to 2021, the study applied a fixed-effects regression model. Results revealed a strong positive correlation, with larger firms demonstrating higher investment in PPE, supported by greater access to credit facilities and internal funding.

Eze and Nnamdi (2023) analyzed the influence of firm profitability on capital expenditure decisions in Nigerian manufacturing firms. The study, covering 2015 to 2022, employed a dynamic panel data analysis technique. Findings revealed that firms with higher profitability levels reinvested a significant portion of earnings into PPE, aiming to improve production efficiency and operational scalability.

Adeola and Adebayo (2023) assessed the impact of firm age on PPE investments in the Nigerian industrial sector. Using secondary data from 2010 to 2020, the study adopted a random-effects panel regression analysis. Findings indicated that older firms invested more in PPE due to accumulated experience, financial stability, and established market presence.

Onyema and Adigun (2023) evaluated the effect of firm age on PPE investments among Nigerian pharmaceutical firms. Using a dataset spanning 2010 to 2020, the study applied a random-effects regression model. Results indicated that older firms invested more significantly in PPE, leveraging their experience and market stability to secure advanced production technologies. Chen and Wong (2023) studied the effect of firm profitability on PPE investments in Asian construction firms. Spanning the period from 2015 to 2023, the study employed a fixed-effects model. Results demonstrated that profitable firms consistently reinvested earnings into PPE to expand their operational capacity and improve competitive advantage.

3. METHODOLOGY

An *ex post facto* design was used in the study based on the fact that the data for the study was secondary which already existed and cannot be controlled. The population of the study consists of quoted non-financial firms on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at December 31, 2023, covering the period 2014-2023. Out of 88 quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria, that formed our sample size, 12 firms have empty financial information within the period under study which was removed. Based on this, a total of 76 firms formed our sample size with 760 observations. The data was collected from the annual accounts and annual accounts of the sample non-financial firms in Nigeria. Panel regression model was used to examine the effect of firm characteristics on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

3.1 Measurement and Operationalization of Variables

Table 1: Variable Measurements

Variable	Proxy	Measurements	Source
Independent			
PPE	Natural logarithm of PPE	Measured as the logarithmic transformation of PPE.	Nijam (2018)& Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, and Tatham (2006),
Size	Firm size	Logarithmic transformation of Total Asset	Onyali & Okafor (2018)
Profitability	Return on assets (ROA)	Measured as the ratio of profit after tax to total assets for the period.	Onyali & Okafor (2018), Okpala & Omaliko (2022)
Firm Age	Age	Measured as the difference between current year and firm listing year.	(Ruan, Tian & Ma, 2011)

Source: Author’s Compilation (2025)

3.2 Model Specification and Justification

In line with the previous researches, the researcher adapted and modified the Model of Hair et al. (2006) in examining the effect of firm characteristics on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This is shown below as thus:

Hair et al. (2006): $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$

The functional model modified for the study is shown below as thus:

PPE = F(FSIZE, ROA, FAGE)

The explicit form of the regression modified for the study is expressed as thus:

$PPE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_2 ROA_{it} + \beta_3 FAGE_{it} + \mu$

Where:

PPE = Property, Plant and Equipment

FSIZE = Firm Size

ROA = Return on Assets

FAGE = Firm Age

μ = Stochastic Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficient of Regression Equation

β_0 = Constant coefficient (intercept) of the model

‘A Priori’ is given as: $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$

Decision Rule: accept Ho if P-value > 1-5% significant level otherwise reject Ho

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
nl_ppe	760	6.621767	.9236931	3.685652	9.143229
fsize	760	7.106919	.8688951	0	9.957177
roa	760	52.80207	24.551	1.53	99.83
age	760	28.72368	13.51727	4	58

Source: STATA 14.2 Computational Results (2024)

From table 2, the descriptive statistics provide valuable insights into the characteristics of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The natural logarithm of property, plant, and equipment (NL_PPE), representing the dependent variable, has a mean of 6.62 with a standard deviation of 0.92. This indicates moderate variability around the average level of investment in property, plant, and equipment. The range spans from 3.69 to 9.14, suggesting significant disparities in asset investment across the sampled firms. Firm size, measured as the logarithmic transformation of total assets, has an average value of 7.11 and a standard deviation of 0.87, reflecting variations in the scale of operations among firms. While the maximum value of 9.96 highlights the presence of some large firms with substantial total assets, the minimum value of 0 may indicate the inclusion of firms with negligible or unrecorded assets. Profitability, expressed as return on assets, has an average value of 52.80%, with a standard deviation of 24.55%. The range, from a minimum of 1.53% to a maximum of 99.83%, suggests that while some firms operate near peak profitability, others have limited returns. Firm age, calculated as the difference between the current year and the listing year, has a mean of 28.72 years and a standard deviation of 13.52 years, indicating that the sample includes both newly listed firms and well-established ones. The youngest firm is 4 years old, while the oldest has been listed for 58 years, demonstrating a broad spectrum of organizational maturity.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	nl_ppe	fsize	roa	age
nl_ppe	1.0000			
fsize	0.8752	1.0000		
roa	0.3860	0.1060	1.0000	
age	0.0758	0.0945	-0.2276	1.0000

Source: STATA 14 Computational Results (2024).

The correlation analysis provides insights into the relationships among the variables in the study. The dependent variable, NL_PPE, shows a strong positive correlation with firm size (FSize), with a correlation coefficient of 0.8752, indicating that larger firms tend to have higher investments in property, plant, and equipment. The correlation between NL_PPE and profitability (ROA) is moderate and positive, with a coefficient of 0.3860, implying that more profitable firms are likely to invest more in property, plant, and equipment. However, a weak positive correlation is observed between NL_PPE and firm age (Fage), with a coefficient of 0.0758, indicating a minimal association between a firm’s age and its tangible asset investments. The results of the positive relationship between the dependent and independent variable shows an interplay of firm characteristics (firm age, firm size and firm profitability) in influencing investments in property, plant, and equipment.

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factors

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
fsize	1.88	0.530680
roa	1.17	0.852044
age	1.09	0.918032
Mean VIF	1.38	

Source: STATA 14.2 Computational Results (2024).

From the table above, the centered VIF ranges from 1.88 to 1.09 which suggests non multi-collinearity feature. Multi-collinearity feature exists when centered VIF exceeds 10 i.e VIF>10

4.1: Test of Hypothesis

Table 5: Random Effect Regression Result on the Effect of Firm Characteristics on PPE of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

Random-effects GLS regression		Number of obs	=	760	
Group variable: id		Number of groups	=	76	
R-sq:		Obs per group:			
within	= 0.2797	min	=	10	
between	= 0.9223	avg	=	10.0	
overall	= 0.8589	max	=	10	
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)		Wald chi2(7)	=	256.89	
		Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	
(Std. Err. adjusted for 76 clusters in id)					
nl_ppe	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
fsize	.6059744	.2177293	2.78	0.005	.1792328 1.032716
roa	.0105053	.0011521	9.12	0.000	.0082472 .0127634
age	.0055186	.0039503	1.40	0.162	-.0022239 .0132611
_cons	1.330351	1.313368	1.01	0.311	-1.243803 3.904506
sigma_u	.23937507				
sigma_e	.22141813				
rho	.53891054	(fraction of variance due to u_i)			

Source: STATA 14.2 Computational Results (2024).

4.2: DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The random effect regression with robust standard errors was performed to assess the impact of various independent variables on the dependent variable nl_ppe. The model was estimated using 760 observations from 76 groups, and the Wald chi-squared statistic for the overall model is 256.89, which is significant at a p-value of 0.0000. This indicates that the model is statistically significant and that at least one of the independent variables has a significant effect on nl_ppe.

The results of the regression are therefore slated below as follows:

H₁: There is no significant influence of Firm size on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

The coefficient for firm size (fsize) as shown on table 5 is 0.6059744, with a p-value of 0.005, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that firm size has a statistically significant positive influence on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. As firm size increases, the amount of property, plant, and equipment (PPE) tends to increase. This finding suggests that larger firms may be better equipped or more financially capable to invest in and maintain significant physical assets. We therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which contends that there is a

significant influence of Firm size on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The implication of this result is that policy-makers, investors, and managers should focus on the expansion of firm size to foster greater investments in physical capital. Firms looking to increase their capital expenditure on PPE should consider growing their size as a means to achieve this objective.

H₂: There is no statistically significant influence of firm profitability on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

The coefficient for firm profitability (ROA) as shown on table 5 is 0.0105053, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates a statistically significant positive influence of firm profitability on PPE. Profitable firms are more likely to invest in PPE as they have the financial resources and capacity to do so. This finding highlights the importance of profitability in determining a firm's ability to acquire physical assets. We therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which contends that there is a statistically significant influence of firm profitability on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The implication is that firms aiming to increase their PPE should focus on improving profitability, as it appears to be a key factor in funding physical asset growth. Investors may also want to consider the profitability of firms when assessing their ability to maintain or expand their physical asset base.

H₃: Firm age has no significant effect on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

The coefficient for firm age (age) as shown on table 5 is 0.0055186, with a p-value of 0.162, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that firm age does not have a statistically significant effect on PPE. Older firms do not necessarily invest more in PPE compared to younger firms. This finding implies that firm maturity does not automatically correlate with increased investments in physical assets, and thus, other factors such as firm size and profitability may be more critical determinants. We therefore rejected the alternate hypothesis and accepted the null hypothesis which contends that firm age has no significant effect on PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. From a policy perspective, this finding suggests that policies aimed at stimulating investment in PPE should not place too much emphasis on the age of firms, as younger firms can also be significant investors in physical capital.

CONCLUSION

This study has explored the effect of firm characteristics on property, plant, and equipment (PPE) of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The findings reveal that firm size and profitability significantly influence PPE investments, underscoring the role of financial resources and profitability in driving capital asset acquisition. Conversely, factors such as firm age was not a significant determinant within the Nigerian context, suggesting that other contextual and macroeconomic factors may moderate their impact. These results align with some prior studies while diverging from others, highlighting the complex and dynamic nature of PPE investment decisions. The study therefore concludes that firm size and profitability determines PPE among the listed firms in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATION

In lieu of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows:

1. Given the significant influence of firm size on PPE investments, firms should prioritize scaling their operations through strategic growth initiatives such as mergers, acquisitions, and market expansions to enhance their capacity for fixed asset acquisition.
2. The significant role of profitability in driving PPE investments underscores the need for firms to focus on cost management, revenue optimization, and operational efficiency to enhance their profitability and reinvestment capacity.
3. As firm age was not a significant factor, older firms should leverage their experience and industry knowledge to innovate and adapt, while younger firms should focus on agility and resource optimization to compete effectively.

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